

WAVELET AND HMM ASSOCIATION FOR ECG SEGMENTATION

Ronan Le Page¹, Karine Provost², Jean-Marc Boucher¹,
Jean-Christophe Cornily², Jean-Jacques Blanc²

¹ Dpt. Signal et Communications, École Nationale Supérieure des Télécommunications de Bretagne,
Technopôle Brest Iroise, BP 832, 29285 Brest, FRANCE

² Service de Cardiologie, Centre Hospitalier Universitaire de la Cavale Blanche,
29200 Brest, FRANCE

e-mail:ronan.lepage@enst-bretagne.fr

ABSTRACT

This paper presents a multiscale Hidden Markov Model (HMM) to improve an automatic segmentation of an electrocardiographic signal (ECG). While the HMM describes the dynamical mean evolution of cardiac cycle, the use of wavelet analysis in association with the HMM leads to take into account local singularities and to obtain better segmentation results. This was tested on a learning base composed of 130 patients.

1 SEGMENTATION OF AN ELECTROCARDIOGRAPHIC SIGNAL (ECG SIGNAL) WITH AN HIDDEN MARKOV MODEL (HMM)

Automatic ECG segmentation is a problem which needs a robust procedure due to the high diversity of signal morphology. An efficient ECG segmentation method [CIB96] using a 10 state HMM, was built with continuous observation densities. In this case, the observation is the local slope of the ECG calculated over 20 ms. This value has been determined after many experimental trials.

1.1 The 10-state Hidden Markov Model

The first order Markov models [Rab89] are characterized by the property that the state at time t only depends on the state it was at time $t - 1$, older dependencies in time are not taken into account.

We describe the observation and the corresponding heart activation states (cf Figure 1) :

1. state *iso1*: isoelectrical line: no activation
2. state P_1 : (positive slope of P-wave): first part of atrial activation
3. state P_2 : (negative slope of P-wave): second part of atrial activation
4. state *iso2*: isoelectrical line: no activation
5. state Q_1 : (positive slope of QRS-complex): first part of ventricular activation
6. state Q_2 : (negative slope of QRS-complex): second part of ventricular activation

The 10 states corresponding to the slope of the signal

Figure 1: 10 state HMM

7. state *iso3*: isoelectrical line: no activation
8. state T_1 : (positive slope of T-wave): first part of ventricular repolarization
9. state T_2 : (negative slope of T-wave): second part of ventricular repolarization
10. state *iso4*: isoelectrical line: no activation

The model is not fully connected, *i.e.* transitions from one step to another are not always possible. The authorized transitions between states are drawn on figure 2.

The Markov model is said hidden because we have only access to a noisy information and not at the states themselves. To estimate the probability densities, a data base was designed with a sufficient number of various cases. The probability density matrices were calculated using a kernel method [CIB96].

Figure 2: Authorized transitions between the 10 states

1.2 Application : P-wave detection

The P-wave is the part of the ECG (cf figure 1) which corresponds to atrial contraction. The P-wave is usually smaller than the other waves, therefore it is hard to detect it. The duration of the P-wave is a parameter for characterizing a frequent heart arrhythmia named Atrial Fibrillation (AF). P-wave duration over 120 ms often means risks of AF. We have a data base of 130 ECG signals (lead II), some relatively noisy.

Two cardiologists, using their medical experience, per-

Figure 3: Comparison between manual segmentations

formed a manual segmentation of the P-wave. We compared it to an automatic segmentation based on our HMM model. Our final goal is to perform an automatic segmentation the closer as possible as the manual ones. On figure 3, we compared the manual segmentations and calculated the coefficient of correlation and the standard deviation whose values are 87% and 7, respectively. On figure 4, we draw the HMM segmentation (vertically) versus the mean of manual segmentation (horizontally); the coefficient of correlation is 89% and the standard deviation 12.

Although good segmentation results were obtained, they were not as reliable as those obtained by manual segmentation by specialists. Generally, the HMM fails because of cases that were not taken into account in the

Figure 4: Comparison between HMM and manual segmentation :

data base used for training the model. Wrong segmentations are due to :

- the weakness of the P-wave
- the presence of too much noise
- a problem of gain
- the fixed length of 20 ms for calculating the slope which maybe inaccurate for some signals

2 ASSOCIATION OF WAVELETS AND HIDDEN MARKOV MODEL

The ability of wavelets for detecting breaks and singularities in signals was shown in the book of Mallat [Mal98]. Wavelets have jointly good time and frequency localization properties. Wavelets are useful to search into the signal the localization (in time) where there are irregularities (strong variations *i.e.* high frequencies).

Some previous work was done on the comparison of the ECG segmentation by wavelets and HMM [PCB98]. In this paper, we try to combine both methods.

2.1 ECG segmentation with 2 state HMM

In a first attempt to associate HMM with wavelet analysis, Crouse and al. [CBN98] [CrB97] proposed to use a two state model with wavelet coefficient measurements in order to improve segmentation. This model supposes that each wavelet coefficient can be modelled, knowing the state, by a gaussian of *zero mean low variance* for high value coefficients (state 1) or *zero mean high variance* for low value coefficients (state2). In figure 5, we verify that wavelet coefficients have such a structure, that means a two state gaussian mixture model.

Figure 5: Two state Gaussian mixture model of wavelet coefficients of an ECG signal

The parameters of this HMM model (means, variances and transition probabilities) are estimated using EM algorithm. We applied this method, but we modified the parameter estimation by using the Stochastic Expectation Maximisation algorithm (SEM) instead of the EM, which avoids to stay in local minima [CD86]. Some good results were obtained at several scales (cf Fig. 6), showing the good localization properties of wavelets, but the results were not as reliable as those obtained with the 10 state HMM method. It is sometimes really difficult to choose the coefficient that represents the beginning, the middle or the end of a wave, when the changes of state are too close or too numerous (cf the state succession for the first P-wave and QRS complex in figure 6).

Figure 6: Wavelet segmentation with two states : a) original signal (with position of the changes of state indicated by “*”), b) wavelet transform (with position of the changes of state indicated by “*”), c) state succession

This lack of efficiency can be explained by the fact that, with only two states, the global knowledge of the

particular dynamical structure of the ECG described in the 10 state HMM is not used. We only try to separate coefficients with high or low value without taking care at what part of the ECG they belong to. The next step is to combine both methods.

2.2 ECG segmentation with 10 state HMM

We decided to try to use wavelets coefficients instead of the local slope in our HMM. The Haar wavelet was chosen for the main following reason : using the Haar wavelet is like performing a first derivative, so the properties of the wavelet coefficients and the slope are close (cf. figure 8).

The scheme of multiresolution analysis is summed up on the figure 7. It is important to say that we do not use any sub-sampled procedure between the different levels of resolution, so we don't have any loss of information at each resolution. We use 4 levels of resolution.

Figure 7: multi resolution analysis

3 APPLICATION TO THE DETECTION OF THE P-WAVE OF ELECTROCARDIOGRAMS

We use the same data base of 130 patients. With the HMM using wavelet coefficients as observation, we also face the same problems of P-wave weakness, noise, . . . , etc. but transients can be seen at different resolution levels, which improves their detection. Sometimes, the problem is to select the resolutions that correctly segment the P-wave. Knowing that normal P-waves have duration between 60 and 190 ms, we can suppress those which are out of these limits (this is the case for resolution 1 and 2 on figure 9 where the P-wave lengths are 55 and 54 ms, respectively). We then take an average decision concerning the P-wave duration.

4 RESULTS AND CONCLUSION

The results are drawn in figure 10 which shows a coefficient of correlation of 94% with a standard deviation of 9. If we compare with the results from figure 4, we can see that we have obtained an automatic segmentation

Figure 8: false P-wave detection with HMM

Figure 9: P-wave detections with multiscale HMM

Figure 10: Comparison between HMM+wavelet and manual segmentation :

with less dispersion. It is shown that by using wavelets and HMM we can improve segmentation results and bring them closer to manual segmentation.

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